

The 5th Conference of the Canadian Network of Scientific Platforms (CNSP), Montreal, Quebec, CANADA

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The Canadian Network of Scientific Platforms (CNSP) is a professional group of scientists, engineers and administrators who represent scientific expertise and research infrastructure platforms across Canada. The CNSP's mission is represented as 4 pillars of values: Advocacy, Education, Networking and Professional Development through which we promote scientific platforms and provide opportunities for our membership of platform scientists and platform administrators, to ensure access to expertise and infrastructure to enable research excellence in Canada.

The last CNSP Scientific Platform Meeting (SPM) took place November 20-22, 2023, in Montreal, Quebec, Canada, with 114 attendees representing, 44 scientific platforms across Canada. The conference took place at the Montreal Neurological Institute 'The Neuro' – an academic medical research center in the core of the city of Montreal, adjacent to and associated with McGill University. It is a unique open science institute which is dedicated to accelerating the discovery and use of new therapeutics and treatments for patients with neurological disorders.

The three-day conference covered one theme per day. Day 1 leveraged the Neuro's focus and represented the concept of Open Science. Open science is a global movement focused on making the scientific process and its discoveries more transparent and freely shared to accelerate discovery {Armeni, 2021 #1229}. This is in direct contrast to the current state of science where a considerable amount of scientific knowledge is currently inaccessible or only accessible for a fee. The Open Science talks were broken up into Initiatives and Resources, and included a panel discussion, the series of talks aligned around how scientific platforms are uniquely posed to foster and promote the goals of open science, which translate into more productive and improved science. Following the Open Science discussions, there were presentations from the awardees for Platform Administrator Award and Platform Scientist Award. The day ended with a conference dinner. Day 2 talks were centered around the importance of scientific platforms to the research community and how infrastructure and expertise in a properly managed facility can accelerate an institution's research goals and help researchers achieve a higher level of excellence. The day concluded with a poster session and networking event. Day 3 focused on the expertise of the scientific platform community by providing a half-day professional development workshop, followed by tours of McGill University's nation-leading scientific platforms.

Day 1: Scientific Platforms as a Road to Open Science

Link to watch and listen: [SPM2023 - Day 1 on YouTube](#)

Welcome Remarks

CNSP President, Claire Brown kicked off SPM 2023 by welcoming its members to The Neuro for the first in-person SPM Conference since 2018. They reflected on the changes in science in Canada since the pandemic and the opportunities that lay ahead for the growing importance and role that scientific platforms play in advancing Canadian research.

Open Science Initiatives

- **What is an Open Science Institute.** Gabriel Pelletier, Open Science Alliance Officer at the Tanenbaum Open Science Institute (TOSI) and the Neuro, presented on: why adopt Open Science principles as an institute and how to put them into practice. These institutes share patient samples, best practices, training and education, and research results. Pelletier presented information about how other institutes can join these networks and benefit not only from shared knowledge, but funding opportunities, partnerships and framework support. Pelletier talked about how these institutes can grow rapidly and collaboratively by pooling their resources together. TOSI offers options for seed projects, where the Open Science capacity is built collaboratively; Buy-in projects which enable institutes to design their own approach to open science, an institute may decide to

adopt Open Science Principles, and if they are aligned with the Neuro's Principles, then TOSI will approve of them, and may contribute financially to the Open Science activities. In exchange, the Institutes participate actively in the TOSI Alliance. Over the long-term, TOSI provides continuous institutional support and community feedback to ensure the success of the programs. Considerations for alternative models within Canadian's network of Open Science institutes were also discussed.

- **Open Science and Drug Discovery.** Thomas Durcan – Director of the Early Drug Discovery Unit (EDDU) at The Neuro –uses patient-derived stem cells and turns them into functional neurons, which can be used for the development of discovery assays and 3D organoid models for personalized medicine and the diagnosis and treatment of neurological disorders. The EDDU, is made up of a team of 30+ researchers who are committed to exploring the use of novel stem cell technologies (such as gene editing, organoid models and multi-omics) to determine the cause of complex neurodegenerative and neurodevelopmental disorders. As an Open Science platform within The Neuro, the EDDU is able to collaborate and share resources, such as their biobank of induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC), and training with other institutes and industry to create long-term strategies to develop and accelerate new therapies. The EDDU activity engages with researchers and industry through 4 working groups, 1) for iPSC phenotyping and gene editing; 2) developing novel assays for discovery and screening; 3) training and outreach to research hospitals and industry, and 4) organoid and tissue engineering. A majority of the EDDU's methods are completely accessible, they maintain a sophisticated database with over 20 protocols, videos and multiple language options. The impact of the EDDU's training and education has resulted in 8 years of successfully research as demonstrated by over 140 iPSC cell lines, 50 training videos, 45 open access publications, 25 industry partnerships, 90 academic studies and hundreds of trainees.
- **Utilizing the Open Science Framework (OSF) for Reproducibility: A Case Study.** Nadja Oertelt, Strategic Partnerships Manager, Center for Open Science (COS) – is a non -profit, established over 10 years ago, based out of Charlottesville, Virginia (USA). Oertelt describes their role as a liaison between consortiums, librarians, policy makers, data managers and institutes that are engaging with COS. The goal of COS is to start, scale and sustain open research practices that democratize access to research, improve stakeholder inclusion and enhance research integrity. The COS provides customization infrastructure and policy solutions to stakeholders and creates incentives to drive more groups to practicing open science. COS provides 3 products, 1) Research software tools, to help researchers manage and share their work; 2) Community Action and Culture Change, to educate and train research communities and engage institutions on incentives to adopt open science policies and; 3) Metascience and Research, to conduct research and collect feedback to evaluate reproducibility and continuously improve inefficiencies in research. Oertelt introduced the Open Science Framework (OSF), the engine behind COS. It is a free online platform which allows researchers to plan, collect, analyze and share their work and it is designed to enable research transparency, permission and sharing that can be customized for each project. Oertelt logged into the OSF platform and did a live demonstration highlighting some of the interesting features, such as collaborative planning tools, finding researchers through their Open Science network and registered reports (a publishing format that allows for peer-review before collecting data).
- **Panel discussion on Open Science & Scientific Platforms.** Moderator Marie-Eve Paquet (CNSP Executive board member) invited Drs. Pelletier, Durcan and Oertelt to share their thoughts on how to measure the benefits of Open Science. Panelist noted that this is something that governing bodies are looking into, and there are metrics for success, such as, how many institutions are joining as Open Science Institutes, how many data sets are shared, accessed and reused by others, numbers of open access publication, etc, and how they are increasing yearly. In the future, The Neuro is planning on benchmarking these metrics and making comparison to larger institutions. A panelist noted that they believed being an open science institute has played some role in their recent success in the recruitment of HQP.
 - There was discussion on the 'Publish or Perish' culture at institutions that value high-impact journals over expensive open access publications, the panelist agreed there is a culture change that needs to happen from the 'top down' to create better incentive to encouraging more open access. Some funding agencies are covering the cost for Early Career Investigators, and there are some services, such as pre-print services or Scholarship Repositories which cover open access

fees at some institutions. It was noted that in the United States some private funding agencies are requiring publications to be open and this push might translate to public funding, and might influence funding agencies in Canada.

- It was noted that running an Open Science Institute may require a more complex administration structure – how can this be achieved and funded? Panelist commented that there are a lot of administrative resources set up at the beginning and due to the novelty of the concept, the most challenging part is determining the most effective route forward. The panelist noted that there is a significant amount of trial and error in developing a proper structure. It was agreed by the panelists that administrative and funding support from their academic institutions had been instrumental in the beginning for setting up their programs. Furthermore, the structure and complexity of teams was eventually streamlined, and adapted to fluctuations in the number of projects.
- Open Science and the growth of AI? The panelist agreed this is an important topic that is currently under evaluation as it is important to balance the need for ease of use with high standards of data security. COS's mission is to build an easily accessible database of free sharing of information and there needs to be a discussion of how that data could be better safeguarded against potential breaches or misuse. Currently, OSF is re-considering their terms of use agreements for how to treat 'AI training sets'. Another panelist commented that data is treated in different tiers based on its sensitivity – for example patient information is very strict and tightly controlled in Open Access, and in the future, one might have to consider doing something similar for other types of data and for futureproofing this data.

Open Science Resources

- **YCharOS: Antibody Characterization through Open Science.** Carl Laflamme, academic associate for The Neuro and the Structural Genomics Consortium – introduced his platform which characterizes antibodies in partnership with YCharOS, a Canadian Open Science group, with the long-term goal to characterize commercially available antibodies for every human protein. To date, they have characterized over 1000 antibodies. Laflamme explains that antibodies are critical for medical research and a reported 40-60% of antibodies do not perform as advertised {Boehm, 2021 #1391}- they do not select the intended protein, or they are non-selective. Laflamme further highlights that this 'reliability crisis' has been debated for 30 years and is ultimately caused by a lack of quality control and results in globally, \$2 billion annually in wasted research funding{Bradbury, 2015 #1233}. The Antibody Characterization lab first receives nomination of antibodies to study through partner pharmaceutical companies and neuroscience collaborators, and through YCharOS, the lab works with numerous commercial companies to provide no-cost antibodies for testing in normal versus target knock-out cell lines for Western Blot, Immunoprecipitation and Immunofluorescence. Once antibodies are characterized, they consolidate the results into one report per protein and upload this report onto the data repository, Zenodo, followed by a peer-reviewed version through F1000 to be published onto PubMed and then SciCrunch portal for viewing. Laflamme demonstrates his platform's process of antibody characterization using several detailed examples from the start point of nomination, to testing, to results and publication. Laflamme concludes by highlighting the need to focus on the 'liability crisis' by ensuring that the antibodies already on the market undergo a stringent quality control measurement before commercialization. Finally, Laflamme notes that the platform is part of the global Structural Genomics Consortium (SGC), an open science group focused on generating high quality protein reagents. Each group in the consortium is dedicated to their own expertise, for example, protein structure, synthetic chemistry, cell-based assay, drug discovery, chemical probes and antibodies.
- **Image informatics training & education: Canadian resources & the BINA AIMM user group.** Judith Lacoste, founding president and scientific director of MIA Cellavie Inc, Montreal, discussed the goal of their group is to foster automated, open, and reproducible science in line with the standards set out by the communities of BioImaging North America (BINA) Automated Image Management and Metadata Annotation (AIMM) user group and the global QUAREP-LiMi (QUality Assessment and REproducibility for Instruments & Images in Light Microscopy) organization. Lacoste reports that they published these standard methods in a special issue of Nature Methods entitled Reporting and Reproducibility in microscopy {Ayoubi, 2023 #1232}. Lacoste emphasized the need for FAIR science, meaning Findable by queries and search, Accessible and authentic, Interoperable with other data types and Reusable with new hypotheses and/or analysis. Currently Tri-agency funders have policies (Tri-agency Research Data Management Policy 2021) that institutions must

have a Research Data Management (RDM) strategy, and all grant recipients are required to deposit all digital research data, metadata and code into a data repository that directly support any pre-print or published research. To achieve this, consistent RDM policies need to be considered nationally and implemented at the institutional level. Currently the RDM strategies between institutions are highly variable and may not meet the same high standards. Lacoste emphasized that policies at these institutions need to consider ongoing RDM practices, well before publication and a policy post-publication to ensure data is FAIR and properly preserved over the long term. Lacoste goes over an international process called REMBI (Recommended Metadata for Bioluminescence) which includes several steps: study, study components, biosamples, specimen, image acquisition, image data, image correlation, and analyzed data. Lacoste notes that REMBI can be applied to any modality, but the example highlights microscopy. The idea of managing FAIR data considers all the steps for data after the acquisition step. Thankfully, Canada has created a national support through the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (DRAC), whose mission is to ensure RDM storage capacity across the country, accessible advanced research computing clusters and encourage the development of software to improve accessibility. Lacoste discusses an example of the workflow of how these resources could be utilized for daily RDM, essentially by taking the image acquisition data and analysis. DRAC provides training resources to utilize their national resources with a variety of popular coding languages. Lacoste then provided a detailed example using a microscopy image of how all these RDM processes and DRAC resources could be used to satisfy the standards, and FAIR practices. Lacoste concludes by noting that cloud-based, open science software – OMERO is being set up in Canada to share data nationally and accessibly that might be a universal solution to the challenge of connecting more institutions and core facilities to data storage solutions and infrastructure. This project was supported with TOSI seed funding, funding from the Molson Foundation and is being implemented under the Canada Bioluminescence (CBI) umbrella. CBI is a CNSP technology node.

Open Systems Neuroscience. Adrien Peyrache, Associate Professor at The Neuro, shared his journey into Open Science, starting with a traditional neuroscience lab that faced challenges in storing and sharing complex neural data. His research focuses on how neurons communicate to form memories and to tackle the data complexity, his research focuses on how neurons communicate, and, to this end, his lab must tackle highly complex data. Taking inspiration from the astronomy tool FITS (Flexible Image Transport System) his group has been involved in the creation, development and adoption of a common format called Neurodata Without Borders (.nwb). This format enabled the breakdown of data into different modalities and made it compatible with common data recording software. In 2022, Peyrache’s team launched Pynapple (Python neural analysis package), a lightweight toolbox for handling physiological and behavioral data using the .nwb format. Pynapple employs object-oriented programming to package data into smaller components, simplifying data analysis and making it possible to easily share analytical scripts, making it reusable and flexible. Peyrache demonstrated how Pynapple works with his own data and outlined future expansions including collaborative libraries (Pynacollada), data visualization (Pynception), logging management (Pynalog), and parallel computing (Pynapples-on-fire).

- **Platform Scientist Awards.**

- **Platform Administrator of the Year Award – Brooke Ring.** Ring is the Manager of Operations and Facilities for the Queen’s CardioPulmonary Unit (QCPU) at Queen’s University in Kingston, Ontario. Ring presented the background and the experience that led them to manage the QCPU core facility. They outlined the unique offerings of their full-service core facility which specializes in translational medicine and offers infrastructure and expertise from bench to bedside and back again. QCPU is a two-part facility which has an onsite Kingston Health Science Centre clinic that hosts clinics and performs echocardiology and pulmonary function testing. The other half is a state-of-the-art research facility which offers services for next-generation sequencing, super-resolution confocal microscopy, flow cytometry, cell culture, histology, and tri-modality CT/PET/SPECT scanning.
- **Platform Scientist of the Year Award – Nhu Trieu.** Trieu is a research technician from the Microscopy and Microanalysis facility at the University of New Brunswick in Fredericton. Trieu emphasized the lesson of ‘not too cool for old school’; and showcases the importance of being a generalist in science by providing lessons from the history of their facility and the collaborations that have allowed it to persevere since the early 1980s when it was established by Gerry Bruce. The

platform features many electron and light microscopes, some of which were acquired 30-40 years ago that are still in operation and provide vital service for the University and global collaborators from 11 countries. Trieu credits its sustainability to the dedication and resourcefulness of its founders and research staff, who have maintained the platform's relevance through flexibility and passion.

Day 1 concluded with a networking dinner and continued conversation about the topics of the day.

Day 2: Accelerating Science Through Scientific Platforms

Link to watch and listen: [SPM2023 - Day 2 on YouTube](#)

- **Keynote Lecture – Supported by the University of Laval CERVO and the Azrieli foundation. “Institutionally supported scientific platform and career path.”** Renee Whan is the Head of the Biomedical Imaging Facility, Katherine Gaus Light Microscopy Facility (KGLMF) and the Executive Director of the Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre (MWAC) at the University of New South Wales (UNSW), Sydney, Australia. Whan’s talk discusses how institutionally supported centers can accelerate research and Whan’s own experience running a world class research infrastructure at UNSW. Whan introduced UNSW as a technology-driven university, presented the research metrics they use to evaluate scientific platforms and gave an overview of the funding landscape in Australia. All of UNSW research infrastructure is housed within the MWAC which serves the entire university and is made up of 6 main locations across campus. There is no infrastructure housed within single investigator laboratories, departments or faculties. All infrastructure is owned by UNSW’s Division of Research. The MWAC has over 300 instruments, including flow cytometry, NMR, radiocarbon dating, microscopy, crystallography, pre-clinical imaging, and spatial transcriptomics; all of which comprises 23 core units and represents an investment of over \$120M (AUD). The center boasts 120 experts as scientists, academics and administrators with salary costs at \$13M (AUD) per year, funded by the University. The center brings in ~\$4M in cost-recovery per year in user fees, and ~\$4-5M (AUD) in research grants for an approximate total of \$8-9M (AUD). There are 2,500 researchers who use the center and generate about ~1,500 publications per year. Metrics show that the center receives ~\$17M (AUD) per year from UNSW to maintain operations. Whan presented the history of the Centre which started in 2007 and how the strategic planning was key to its growth over time. Outside of business planning, one of the most important steps to establish this centre was to introduce internal infrastructure grants and network facilities grants to which any researcher could apply and receive 2 years of funding to establish ‘expertise focused’ cores. Overseeing the MWAC is an executive team which manages 7 expertise focused core facilities, which then direct individual units of infrastructure within those cores. To help in retention of their staff scientists, they created a path for promotion and very clear criteria which, if met, staff can apply for consideration for promotion. Additionally, staff can receive bonuses for taking on extra responsibility to better the center; for example, if a staff scientist is working overtime to establish an RDM process, they will receive extra compensation. Whan explained that their cost-recovery model is varied between their centers and includes, per hour costs, per blocks of hours costs and subscription models. Their goal is to cover their \$4M operational costs, including, infrastructure service, maintenance and consumables. They have one central booking system which was custom designed for MWAC and is available commercially across the world – currently 150 labs utilize this software. A live demonstration included a walkthrough of the software beginning from sample submission to the histology core and explained how it is linked to the staff scientist electronic lab books, protocols and services; which is important for validation, oversight and reliability. This software is key to their growth as it tracks all their operational data and helps strategize how to create new capacity and turnover/replacement of instruments. Whan explained the grants for new equipment and that the path depends on the need, for example – new technology, or researcher-driven need. For replacing aging equipment, they explained their process where they breakdown infrastructure into age demographics depending on the usage and robustness of the technology, for example NMR’s have a longer life-time then flow cytometers. Annually, they retire 4 instruments a year. In 2022, MWAC established a business case for \$7M (AUD) per year for 5 years dedicated to replacing aging infrastructure. For the final part of their presentation, Whan highlighted three facilities under MWAC, the Solid State & Elemental Analysis Unit, The Electron Microscopy Core and the Light Microscopy Core. Whan concluded by discussing the challenges that MWAC needs to focus on in the future: the control and growth of the facilities, staff support for short-term and long-term projects, improving research staff retention and the opportunities of working with more industry partners.

- **Platform Science for Brain Research: A National Strategy's Key to Success.** Jennie Z. Young the Executive Director of the Canadian Brain Research Strategy. They explained that in the field of brain research, Canada has a large coalition of patient advocacy groups, private charities, professional working groups, government-based initiatives, and industry partnerships – but no overarching strategic plan. The goal of the Canadian Brain Research Strategy (CBRS) is to strategically bring these groups together to advocate for the government to invest in a National Brain and Mental Health Initiative. Looking at brain and mental health initiatives around the globe, Canada stands far below other countries in terms of plans and funding initiatives. Much like AI and Quantum computing initiatives the government is already investing in long-term strategies, CBRS is advocating for a strategy for brain science and mental health with a focus on early career researchers as this might be key as Canada has many early career leaders in brain research. Young further explained the strategy proposal will focus on Canada's strengths of Open Science, diversity and team science, neuroethics, platform science, brain-AI interfaces, and transdisciplinary training. They provided examples of conversations with key stakeholders with how the strategies might be crafted. One of the most important conclusions that came out of these conversations was the importance of platforms, especially, in their ability to enable equitable access. Platforms are uniquely positioned to elevate all researchers regardless of institution size, geography and seniority, additionally, they could also connect patients and researchers and improve engagement. CBRS also found that platforms were better at sharing expertise and datasets across disciplines, and due to Canada's limited funding pool for research, platforms can maximize funding investments by efficiently sharing resources and allowing for further investment in state-of-the-art technology. To conclude their talk, they emphasized the importance of moving away from project specific funding to fostering a research ecosystem which invests in open science, training and expertise, and research infrastructure. Their next steps for CBRS include creating a blueprint for a national strategy and engaging the government.
- **Leveraging Short-Term Support for Long-Term Strategy.** Krystle Van Hoof, Managing Director and CEO of the Healthy Brain Healthy Lives (HBHL) Program at McGill University, which is funded by the Canada First Research Excellence Fund (CFREF). HBHL was established in 2016 and runs until 2026 with the goal of creating a global center of excellence for neuroinformatics and to accelerate translational discoveries to improve brain health. They explained that HBHL does this using 4 funded strategies to: Develop Capacity, Advance Discovery, Accelerate Innovation and Translate Knowledge. The most heavily funded strategy was for developing capacity, which involved the creation and stabilization of 9 core facilities and technology platforms at McGill alone. They explained that the core funding was separated into rounds over the 10-year period (an initial strategic call, a renewal call and an open call for more facilities) and they wanted to share their insight into what they have learned through the process. The objectives for establishing core facilities were to foster international collaborations, retain and attract talent, produce world-class research, and ensure long-term stability. Each core facility was to track these metrics and report annually to HBHL as part of a milestone review. It was transformative for their strategic planning. Another helpful support from HBHL was establishing a sustainability workshop and providing business development support to be utilized by the cores. The key components that proved helpful from this process were engaging with higher administration about cost efficiencies and sustainability, exploring userbase expansion, gaining new services and expertise to market to users, creating SMART goals (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound), and systematizing existing skills for a fee. On the technology side, some helpful outcomes included moving from collaborative agreements to fee-for-service agreements, engaging with private donors, increasing hours to include evenings and weekends (mostly for private sector users), charging more during peak hours, and merging units. The feedback they heard from the cores was that they needed more financial support, business development support, help making connections to industry, regulatory support, prioritization for external funding and advocating for appropriate wages. They concluded that creating central support for core facilities requires a patchwork approach and should consider a range of options and encourage an economy of scale where sharing resources and expertise between cores is mutually beneficial and sustainable.
- **UHN Research and Innovation Cores – Modus Operandi.** Luke Brzozowski, the Executive Director of the Translational Research & Core Facilities, University Health Network (UHN), Toronto, Ontario presented about their experience running the largest network of core facilities in Canada. Brzozowski explained that UHN is a network of numerous, research focused hospitals in the Toronto area which perform foundational,

translational and clinical research. UHN has over 1,194 principal investigators, 3,845 staff and trainees, 1M sq ft of research space and \$500+M in research funding. It is all managed under the department of Research Solutions and Services. Brzozowski outlined the detailed structures of support that make up the department and explained how 21 core facilities are integrated together to create one research and innovation core. Each core is treated as its own business unit and is managed by a core manager who is a staff scientist who operates independently of the principal investigators (PIs) who use the facilities. Brzozowski acknowledged this is a unique structure in Canada, but that it has proved very successful. They also noted that each unit has its own budget and fiscal projections so they can celebrate their own successes and address their own challenges. In terms of governance, each core has a scientific advisory board, and all cores are operated under the Executive Vice Principal of Science and Research, a department and a research council executive. Due to their size, the network of cores offers all services that any researcher could need including diverse infrastructures for sequencing, cell culturing, imaging, flow and NMR. Brzozowski explained that they centralized common practices including external business development, infrastructure strategy, branding and marketing, financial oversight and billing, inter-departmental relations, escalated issues, and temporary personnel. Next, they focused on the finances of the Research and Innovation cores, highlighting that most of their revenue comes from internal UHN users, but other factors include modest direct subsidies from the institution, while 37% are provided by external academics and external industry. They highlighted that since 2019 their revenue has grown 5.6% and now 84% of total operational costs are recovered from fees. This was achieved by categorizing all cores into two financial models. Type 1 cores make up the majority and are not responsible for rent or paying for support, all external work is marked up by 40% and they may receive subsidies. Type 2 cores set their own margins and overhead, they pay for rent and research support and support the majority of all the external users. Brzozowski followed up with some examples of how industry utilizes different types of partnership depending on their size and the scale of the project, they discussed a multitude of custom strategy pipelines that have been effective in growing industry collaboration. Brzozowski concluded his talk by noting that core facilities are bringing about a culture change which debates federalist vs centralist mentalities. They shared a message that even cores as substantial as theirs are still a work in progress, and it's about continuously getting your house in order.

- **Panel Discussion - Accelerating Science through Scientific Platforms.** Moderator Marie-Eve Paquet (CNSP Executive board member) invited Drs. Whan, Young, Van Hoof, and Brzozowski to the front to begin their panel. Paquet asks Brzozowski, who among their institute leads CFI applications, is it by core or executive committee? Brzozowski explains that it is debated often, and it varies, but they all agree on the guidelines that the research project and CFI infrastructure application must contribute to high quality research, the PI must come with a 'heavy resume', and it needs to be geographically advantageous. Brzozowski noted that at UHN a portion of their CFI funding envelop is now dedicated to core facilities, and they involve core facility managers in deciding where equipment should go. Whan echoed the importance of involving core managers in the placement of equipment, to make sure it's a good fit for the service, the users and that it ensures that the applicant PI has a good relationship with the core.
 - Discussion included what is the benchmark of sustainability for core facilities and what measure of cost-recovery needs to be achieved? The panelist agreed it depends and varies across cores, but that sustainability is often breaking even on revenue and expenditures. Some panelists note that it is still too early to say if core facilities are stable since their growing importance in Canada is still recent, which is why centralization seems to be key to core facilities success. Brzozowski notes for the UHN model that the bonus of centralization is that some cores are highly profitable and if they make more than 150% revenue, a portion of their profits go to subsidies of less profitable cores. Brzozowski mentioned the importance of considering continuous subsidy support to accelerate less-profitable cores, and when a core grows enough to become profitable, they get to keep their profits as an achievement until the 150% mark. Whan noted that each country has their own government contribution to cores and sustainability looks different around the world, but what they have in common is that cores cannot recover all the salary and operation costs. They cannot be sustained on fees from research grants alone, they need investment from institutions and government. Whan continued that the best place to start on sustainability is to make sure staff are offered permanent positions with a clear career path.
 - Where should business acumen be instilled in core facilities? Should the scientists, especially young

scientists entering the field, receive business training, or should it be obtained by external consultation? Van Hoof believes scientists already do too much, and they should be free to focus on the science. They would urge institutions to provide professional business management support to cores. In contrast, Whan believes scientists with some business experience can really inform the best practices. Young notes that there should be a path for scientists to gain more business and managerial experience as there is a need to fill in the years to come, referring to the culture change arising from core facilities. Brzozowski agrees a scientist with a strong business acumen is invaluable for making strategic partnerships with industry or even philanthropy.

- What made your institutions work with and support cores? Brzozowski simply remarks that it was necessity because of limited financial resources. In their situation they were given no choice but to figure out a way to make the core facilities profitable, or they would no longer receive funding – they acknowledge the work of a few core managers that created an innovative plan that worked. Brzozowski also relied heavily on their commercialization office to pair cores with industry, and this non-academic, contract-focused (rather than collaborative), core facility service agreement route was key to their success and eventually contributed heavily to the academic achievements later-on because the core facilities ‘still existed’ to provide service to the academic community.
- How do successful core facilities manage training? Should there be a move to practical training for servicing of instruments for core staff and similarly, specific training for operating equipment in a core facility for the application specialist? There is agreement among the panel that it seems like there should be more opportunities to partner with vendors for more training. Whan notes that there are agreements at their facilities to train vendors application scientists at their facility in technical support and claims that because of this relationship they do not have service agreements at their facilities. This has become popular in multiple institutions in Australia. They urge building great relationships with vendors to find solutions to maintaining equipment. Brzozowski notes pitting vendors against their competitors towards a mutual goal can often bring about a reciprocal training environment.
- Where is the balance between revenue generating workhorse equipment and specialized innovative equipment? The panel discusses the importance of making strategic decisions with an emphasis on sustainability, but a similar focus on research excellence is incredibly valuable in terms of discovery. It’s important to be financially successful enough to subsidize the innovative equipment and allow time for research and development or they recommend seeking out philanthropic support for cutting edge equipment.

Science Networks & Stakeholders

- **Plenary Talk: Canadian Science Policy Centre.** Mehrdad Hariri, President of the Canadian Science Policy Centre (CSPC), talks about their national network which was established in 2009. Their mandate is to be at the center of where science meets policy, innovation and technology which contributes to the well-being of Canadians. CSPC is a non-partisan, non-for-profit and a non-advocate organization with a mission to be an inclusive hub for connectivity, convening, capacity building and catalyzing research in support of a science policy community. They have a multi-faceted approach to reaching these goals which include, youth engagement, integrated perspective (examining diverse views from multidisciplinary issues), public engagement and partnership. For their talk, Hariri shares stories of new ideas and passion that have come out of CSPC. They explain that CSPC origins grew out of the lack of interaction between researchers, institutions and the policy makers in Canada and began by building a community of fellow researchers and trainees who recognize this disconnect as an issue of national importance. CSPC’s popularity is due to Canada having the second most decentralized form of government in the world, the regions are so disconnected that most institutions have complete autonomy and set their own policies – leading to significant gaps across broad fields. CSPC saw an opportunity to level the playing field to make sure all stakeholders in science could rise together. Currently, CSPC is made up of 4 full time staff and they have a dedicated ‘army’ of volunteers, mostly made up of science policy trainees from across Canada. Outside of their very popular annual conference, which is attended by over 1000+ members, they provide awards, have an annual magazine about science policy and have an initiative called ‘Science meets Parliament’ where early-career researchers and trainees from across Canada are selected for multiple policy training sessions and go to Parliament for a day to have lengthy engagement with policy makers to better understand and learn from each other. Hariri notes that due to conflict of interest, CSPC does not benefit from government funding,

and they are instead self-funded. CSPC has been successful in building a nationally connected community and their impact can be measured in successful initiatives where they have positively shifted the discourse on science policy by engaging and inspiring youth, build capacity for future generations and celebrated excellence in policy innovation.

For the second half of the talk, Hariri spoke candidly and shared views on science policy in Canada. Hariri begin by providing data on a global scale where Canada's investment in research and development (R&D) sits at 1.54% of GDP (2019), which falls well below the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's) average of 2.47% investment. The gap between the OECD average and Canada's standing over the past 20 years has significantly widened to a shortfall of approximately \$22B, despite numerous governments initiated national reports which have outlined the critical need for more investment and innovation. The landscape in Canada over the past 3-5 years has been lacking in short-term and long-term investment, insufficient coordination among federal, provincial and territories, with many more gaps to fill. Thankfully, there is progress in 1) updating mechanisms for multidisciplinary research, 2) engaging young investigators, and 3) developing better coordination mechanisms between funding agencies, as well as equity diversity and inclusion (EDI) campaigns for fair and equitable research. Going into the details of the Canadian economy, the 2 primary performers of research and development (R&D) in Canada are higher education and business sectors. Hariri further notes that Canada represents 3.8% of the worlds research output, but this figure has been continuously falling each year; the country's research strengths are in psychology and cognitive behavior, visual & performing arts, philosophy & theology, earth & environmental sciences, and public health & services. The Council of Canadian Academics report on R&D in Canada in 2018 concluded that Canada's standing in R&D is at risk without proper investment in private and public R&D sectors, the research we are producing is not as impactful as other countries on most enabling and strategic technologies and the country's research is less specialized and esteemed in core fields of natural sciences and engineering. They concluded that Canada has a lot of work to do, and it may be critical that they match OECD's average in R&D investment, they note that the benefits of doing so might generate wealth by improving the diversity of exports, expanding our market to more countries which will grow the business sector.

IRDQ: Québec portal to cutting-edge infrastructures in advanced materials. Sébastien Garbarino from PRIMA Québec discussed the role of the Infrastructures for Research & Development network (IRDQ) in supporting Quebec's material sciences sector. PRIMA Québec, a non-profit hub, enhances research and innovation across three categorized sectors: basic materials, finished and semi-finished products, and process & instrumentation, aimed at funding collaborative research projects involving industrial partners. Since 2015, PRIMA Québec has facilitated over 181 projects with a combined funding of \$47,5M, collaborating with more than 250 industry partners and academic institutes, which has led to the creation of 97 pieces of intellectual property, 402 publications, and the training of 789 highly qualified personnel. The IRDQ network under PRIMA Québec notably supports the material sciences ecosystem by matching industry partners with academic facilities and expertise, promoting high-quality science and sustainability to both the industrial and academic R&D community.

- **Building the Canadian Deep Tech Ecosystem.** Marie D'lorio, President of Deep Tech Canada, explained that 'Deep tech' represents an innovation revolution in science. D'lorio further explained that 'Deep Tech' is the challenge-focus approach to using technologies to solve global problems, create new markets and disrupt existing technologies. The estimated impact of deep tech by 2032 is \$3.73B and could benefit many sectors including agritech & food, climate action & energy, communication & security, health & medicine, and transportation & exploration. By focusing resources on solving a specific problem, it tends to be more efficient than the more traditional route of collecting seed funding and undergoing multiple competitions. Deep Tech Canada's vision is to position Canada as a global leader in tackling pressing global issues through a collaborative approach to cutting-edge innovation. Deep Tech's mission is to strategize partnerships to build a flexible and competitive ecosystem within Canada to create solutions for these global issues. They note that success in this field is all about building meaningful connections over long periods of time, and eventually it leads to economic attainment. D'lorio's approach to building a national strategy begins with increasing Canada's competitiveness in the global marketplace; supporting cross-disciplinary training of tomorrow's workforce; catalyzing high impact projects that drive meaningful change; and accelerating commercialization of emerging tech in Canada. They shared their philosophy of building culture change

through community, strongly believing in convening for learning about the diversity of intersecting perspectives and stories from trainees, academics, entrepreneurs and conveyors. They emphasized that this process takes commitment and patience, but that the reward is well worth it. The services provided by Deep Tech Canada include strategic planning, technology scouting, challenge-based workshops, networking events and conferences, and data analytics. D'Iorio illustrated the specific services that Deep Tech Canada provides by telling stories of successful collaborations and start-ups.

- **Creating a vibrant and sustainable semiconductor industry in Canada.** Gordon Harling, President and CEO of CMC Microsystems presented their non-profit organization that was established in 1984. CMC Microsystems provides services to simplify access and reduce costs for advanced technology such as microelectronics, photonics, Edge AI, nanofabrication and quantum technologies. Harling noted that they have a national network which has supported 10,000+ academic and industry partners at 68 universities and colleges. In 2023 alone, they enabled 12 new start-ups and 790 HQP moved to industry jobs in Canada. They also have an impressive global network of ~90 institutions across 19 countries. Their services are classified into 3 areas: CAD – state-of-the-art software and design; FAB – simple access and reduced cost for working prototypes; and LAB – tools for tests and demonstration. Based on the classification, they have a unique virtual incubator environment which allows start-ups access to powerful software, test equipment, and computing power, for a yearly subscription fee. CMC involvement is essential for most start-ups to access these unique but costly software and tools, and significantly accelerate their impact. In 3 years, they have helped establish 1,220 prototypes, with 483 prototypes being developed in 2023 alone. Harling concluded by emphasizing the importance and impact of Canada's semiconductor sector, which is industry leading and Canada's up-and-coming sectors in-silicon photonics, and superconductors. An exciting development was a Canada-United States partnership to create a semiconductor corridor which could revolutionize this industry in Canada.
- **Panel Discussion: Partnership with Industry.** Moderator Derek Oliver (CNSP Executive board member) invites Drs. Garbarino, D'Iorio and Harling to the front to begin their panel. Oliver opens the questioning by asking what were the 'surprises' they faced as their networks grew? Harling reflects on 45 years in the semiconductor industry, and that the speed in which the technology develops still astounds him, giving an example of starting in microns and now developing functions in nanometers and now with upcoming AI technologies, they believe that speed will increase 10-fold. D'Iorio recounts the numerous times that politics have stifled the growth of their sector as provinces are not always interested in investing in a federal solution to a pan-Canada benefit. Garbarino echoes the provincial sentiments and notes politics can also be a frustrating process for creating international partnerships.
 - Discussion turns to gaps in government funding of graduate and colleges versus undergraduate/high school education and if industry could play a part finding solutions to getting technology to students earlier? Would they see a benefit in the industry? Harling and D'Iorio comment that the graduate and college levels are viewed the same and have similar levels of enrolment. Academia is a complementary fit to industries goals of exploring new ideas and benefiting from training.
 - Are there any plans to expand Prima Quebec to other sectors? Garbarino notes there are some conversations with other sites about their model, but they are in preliminary stages – they have been approached by CFI Navigator with an idea to pair industry with institutional core facilities which might serve to open more lines between industry and academia, but they are unsure if it is the right choice.
 - When asked if the panel had advice for CNSP on finding funding for the creation of a network, Harling suggests exploring new business development opportunities and to be mindful of sharing the benefits of a new networks with those that will benefit the most. D'Iorio notes that you need to have an idea of the local economic benefit to apply for provincial funding and the contribution of the pan-Canadian membership to apply for federal funding – they suggest establishing a strong financial model that demonstrates that the membership has 'skin in the game'.
 - How is the deep tech industry including social sciences in their development? There is a sense that if their input was included earlier, some of the concerns with misuse of technology might have been avoided (ex. Policies on AI and climate change). D'Iorio notes that their industry benefited from multiple townhall panels where a diverse range of opinions were voiced from policy makers, humanities, social sciences etc. They are very excited about a 'Renaissance' of deep tech industries

advancing by incorporating more disciplines from the beginning, so long as the goal of what needs to be achieved is clear, D'lorio believes the gaps in knowledge can be filled with expertise. Harling reflects that the sciences are good at covering the 'how' and the humanities are there to ask 'why' and those are very tough questions to address, if scientists asked ourselves the 'why' more often we might avoid the concerns we all have about, for example, AI growing too fast.

Poster Session/Wine & Cheese Networking Event – Bellini Life Science Building Atrium (Table 1).

Day 3 - Professional Development Workshop

Link to watch and listen: [SPM2023 - Day 3 on YouTube](#)

- **Power Skills in Academic Environments.** Pierre-Jean Alarco, Knowledge Mobilization & Community Engagement Officer, Polytechnique Montreal, hosted an engaging 3-hour, introductory workshop on professional development for academic environments. In the workshop they introduced the concept of Power Skills, how these skills might be similar or different in the academic ecosystem, discussed considerations for training and employed a group activity which put participants skills into practice. they opened by explaining that 'Power Skills', traditionally known as Soft Skills, is an umbrella term which encompasses skills that are not technical, Alarco references several studies conducted by the European University College Association that investigated what skills students entering the labor forces in sciences needed to have to succeed in the field and included skills in Problem-solving, Collaboration, Communication, Flexibility, Empathy, Perseverance and Presentation Skills. Looking specifically at the data of a study they conducted in 2021 on the key power skills of research teams resulted in an outcome of 6 key skills: Communication, Leadership, Resiliency & Adaptability, Professionalism & Integrity, Collaboration & Promotion and the overarching ability of Problem Solving. Alarco broke down the specifics of each key skill into 5-6 more specific traits and linked the key skills to where they benefited the team versus individual goals. Alarco provides detailed scenarios to illustrate how key skills can be used to accomplish team and individual goals. After summarizing the key skills, Alarco presented common real-life scenarios in the academic environment and engaged participants to give their thoughts on solutions using the key skills. Some of the scenarios were 'How would you respond' to, for example, an employee who is consistently not completing tasks, and a report being rushed to completion without detailed review.
- For the second hour of the workshop, Alarco presented their NSERC Create grant: OPSIDIAN (Optimized Power Skills in Interdisciplinary, Diverse & Innovative Academic Networks). OPSIDIAN offers trainees an innovative training program to acquire and experience/apply the fundamentals of Power Skills and integrate them into conducting science in the present and future. The objectives of the program are: Interdisciplinarity (bilateral interaction of several disciplines), Diversity (scientific heterogeneity and/or identity in research teams) and Learning approach (experimenting/consolidating these Power Skills in authentic situations). What makes OPSIDIAN unique is the understanding of the learning cycle of 'skill acquisition' versus 'skill application' and the evolution of each cycle as you learn and change with each new skill.
- The final part of the workshop combined the powerskills with the learning approach of OPSIDIAN, in a case study. Alarco noted that its best to use a case study scenario that is not in the specialized field of the participants and that the subject should not be contentious. The case study for this workshop regarded the building of a nuclear storage site at Chalk River. The participants were presented with two sides of an argument for whether to build the nuclear storage site or not and divided into small groups to discuss possible outcomes. Each group presented their method of resolution and their justifications. Alarco concluded the workshop by noting that all the groups came to a similar consensus with different nuances and thanked everyone for their participation.

Closing Remarks

CNSP President Claire Brown concludes SPM 2023 by highlighting some of the initiatives for CNSP for 2024, such as planning the next SPM, regional events during 2024, continued advocacy to support scientific platforms and platform scientists at a national level and creation of the 2024-2029 CNSP Strategic plan. Brown thanked all members of the CNSP executive for their hard work in planning the program and logistics for the conference. Brown gives special thanks to the events and logistic coordination team from the Neuro and Curly Dog Communications for helping run a fantastic conference.

Acknowledgement:

The CNSP is sincerely grateful to their sponsors, without their support it would not be possible to hold the conference. CNSP acknowledges the contributions of Advanced Bioimaging facility (ABIF), Azrieli Foundation, UHN, University of Ottawa, Sick Kids, IDT, Stratocore, Qiagen, Tannenbaum Open Science Institute, D-Mark Biosciences, StemCell Technologies, Agilent/iLab, Leica, Evident Scientific, Canadian Institute for Health Research (CIHR), Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, McGill School of Biomedical Sciences, Centre CERVO

Scientific Platform Tours. Several scientific platforms at McGill University were showcased by guided tours for small groups of CNSP members. One group toured, *A) Chemistry and Material Structure Sciences Platforms at the Downtown Campus* including 1) The Facility for Electron Microscopy Research; 2) McGill Nanotools Microfab; 3) McGill Institute for Advances Materials and; the McGill Chemistry Characterization Facility. The second group was *B) Life Sciences platforms within the Bellini Life Sciences Complex* and included the 1) Advances Bioimaging Facility (ABIF); 2) Metabolomics Innovation Resource; 3) Single Cell Imaging & Mass Cytometry Analysis Platform and 4) Flow Cytometry Core Facility.

Table 1 – Abstract for the SPM2023 Poster Session. Winners for the ‘Best Poster’ are noted by *Best Poster

001	
Title	CBRAIN: a web-based, distributed computing platform for collaborative neuroinformatics Research
Author (s)	Bryan Caron, Reza Adalat, Natacha Beck, Serge Boroday, Samir Das, Najmeh Khalili-Mahani, Darcy Quesnel, Pierre Rioux, Darius Valvicius, Alan Evans.
Location	McGill Centre for Integrative Neuroscience (MCIN),
Description	CBRAIN (https://cbrain.ca) is an open source, web-based, collaborative research software platform designed to address major challenges in big data research. CBRAIN provides researchers in neuroinformatics, genomics and more the ability to easily collaborate, store and analyze data at scale using computational pipelines on heterogeneous computing and data resources around the world. CBRAIN is used in numerous major neuroinformatics projects and is a pillar component of NeuroHub (https://neurohub.ca), a core platform of McGill University’s Healthy Brains, Healthy Lives initiative (https://www.mcgill.ca/hbhl/). In production since 2009, CBRAIN is a mature and flexible orchestration infrastructure seamlessly connecting scientists to a network of advanced computing and data resources. While CBRAIN is primarily used for applications in brain science, it is a completely general platform that could be used in other settings.
002	
Title	Structural Biology Platform at Université de Montréal
Authors	Normand Cyr
Location	Faculté de médecine, Université de Montréal
Description	Exploring the spatial organization of biological molecules is crucial to structural biology research, unraveling the connections between structure and function. The Structural Biology Platform at Université de Montréal, established in 2018 with funding from the CFI, houses 3 high-field NMR spectrometers (500, 600 and 700 MHz), and a small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) system capable of high-throughput analysis, and inline chromatography for SEC-SAXS experiments. An integrated structural bioinformatics platform supports resource-intensive data analysis, including structure prediction using AlphaFold. Complementary biophysical tools encompass SEC-MALS, ITC, and robotics for crystal tray preparation. Philanthropic contributions and recent government grants have recently enabled the acquisition of two cutting-edge cryo-electron microscopes (cryo-EM). These microscopes will revolutionize our ability to explore complex biological structures, offering invaluable insights at the molecular level.
003	
Title	MAPLES: Montreal Area Platform for Electrochemical Systems
Authors	Eric R. Dionne
Location	Université de Montréal
Description	The MAPLES technology platform was created to accelerate research in functional energy-related materials and devices, from lithium-ion batteries to electrochromic displays and solar panels. Most

	MAPLES instruments allow studies of electrochemical systems in their intended position of use (in situ) and during operation (in operando) to fully identify the factors limiting the performance of these systems. This infrastructure is also fully accessible to the materials science community. Indeed, we can meet the needs for research and characterization of materials/devices in various fields such as the optimization of (opto)electronic devices, from the development of drugs and pharmaceutical products to complex analyzes of environmental samples. You can visit our website at www.maples.umontreal.ca to get an overview of our infrastructure. Our operator, on site, will be able to answer your questions
004	
Title	UDM Regional Center for Mass Spectrometry
Authors	Alexandra Furtos
Location	Universite de Montreal, Department of Chemistry
Description	The mass spectrometry regional center comprises over a dozen LC-MS, GC-MS and SFC-MS state-of-the-art instruments located in the brand-new campus MIL. The MS platform is run by three full-time scientists whose combined expertise encompasses an exceptionally large variety of applications. This goes from developing and upscaling chromatographic separations to drug metabolism, pharmacokinetics, structure confirmation, environmental analyses. Examples of services involving nominal mass, accurate mass, purity, enantiomeric ratio, residual solvent determinations as well as quantification of endogenous and exogenous species in complex matrices will be presented.
005	
Title	Development of an Open Science Collection of Patient-derived iPSCs for Studying Disease Mechanisms in Neurodegenerative Diseases
Authors	Taylor M Goldsmith(1), Carol X-Q. Chen(1), Nicolas Ferry(2), Narges Abdian(1), Zhipeng You(1), Michael Nicouleau(1), Marie-Noëlle Boivin(2), Lydiane Gaborieau(2), Peng Wang(2), Kevin LaFleur(2), Sophiya Enjambre(2), Jason Karamchandani(2), Thomas M. Durcan(1).
Location	1. The Neuro's Early Drug Discovery Unit, Montreal, QC. 2. The Neuro's Clinical Biological Imaging and Genetic Repository (C-BIG), Montreal, QC.
Description	An open science collection of patient-derived iPSCs has been established at The Neuro through a collaboration between the Clinical, Biological, Imaging, and Genetic Repository (C-BIG) and the Early Drug Discovery Unit (EDDU). C-BIG is a collection of biologic samples, clinical information, imaging, and genetic data from patients with neurologic diseases as well as from health controls. The data and samples at C-BIG are accessible to research teams around the world, congruent with open science principles. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) from consenting healthy and diseased donors are then reprogrammed by the EDDU and edited using CRISPR-Cas9 technology to create knock-outs, knock-ins, and isogenic controls. iPSCs are differentiated into different neural subtypes for the study of neurodegenerative diseases. Generated iPSCs are then banked with C-BIG and are available for global distribution on a cost-recovery basis.
006	
Title	ALLS. A National high-power laser user facility
Authors	Heide Ibrahim
Location	ALLS, INRS-EMT, Varennes, QC, Canada
Description	The Advanced Laser Light Source (ALLS) is a unique laser-based infrastructure providing a coherent rainbow of light and cutting-edge end-stations to its users. The facility is located at INRS-EMT, close to Montreal. It is home of the most powerful laser in Canada with 750 TW, as well as to high repetition rate laser systems to explore novel phenomena in matter with ultrafast tools. alls.inrs.ca
007	*Best Poster
Title	The Advanced Optical Microscopy Facility at University Health Network
Authors	Xiaotian (Tag) Yu and James Jonkman
Location	University Health Network, Toronto, ON,
Description	Accelerate breakthrough technologies by tapping into a world-class imaging facility. Located in Toronto, Canada, the Advanced Optical Microscopy Facility (AOMF) is a premier destination for University Health Network researchers as well as external collaborators from academia and

	industry. In addition to our state-of-the-art imaging equipment, users can tap into a multidisciplinary team of biologists, chemists, physicists, and neuroscientists dedicated to supporting their microscopy imaging goals. Check out our website at www.aomf.ca for key resources to jumpstart your imaging project, including instrument details, webinars, facility locations, informative papers, and more!
008	*Best Poster
Title	The automation and screening platform with iPSC derived cells at the Neuro's EDDU
Authors	Andrea I. Krahn, Wolfgang E. Reintsch, Thomas M. Durcan
Location	The Neuro's Early Drug Discovery Unit (EDDU), McGill University, Montreal, QC, Canada
Description	The Early Drug Discovery Unit (EDDU) at the Neuro facilitates research by using human induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC) for both fundamental and discovery-based research projects. These iPSCs can be made into a variety of different patient-derived cell types to model diseases. The EDDU's automation and screening platform provides instruments and expertise to develop and execute high content and high throughput screening. The instrumentation allows for the miniaturization of assays developed at the EDDU and by external partners into 96 or 384 well microplate format, though we can also work with custom formats. By automating all assay steps, from plate coating, cell seeding, media change, compound/reagent addition, fixation, staining, image acquisition, and image analysis, throughput and reproducibility are increased. This enables the investigation of complex 2D or 3D cellular systems for functional and drug discovery studies.
009	
Title	Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM) At The Laboratory of Characterization of Materials (LCM)
Authors	Patricia Moraille
Location	Département de chimie, Université de Montréal
Description	Since January 2001, the Laboratory for the Characterization of Materials (LCM) offers Quebec's research community access to a variety of state-of-the-art instruments. Research professionals provide training as well as technical support. We describe here, the various scanning probe microscopy (SPM) options that are available at the LCM. Beyond imaging topography, SPM can use a variety of forces to measure friction, visco-elasticity and compositional variations. SPM as a technique is not bound to specific environmental conditions, It can be performed in vacuum, air or water and at a variety of temperatures. The expertise and savoir-faire of this Lab makes it one of Quebec's specialized infrastructures for the imaging of nanostructured materials and thin films on the nanometer to micron length scales. Our SPM installation is used by more than 100 scientists yearly. Our facilities are opened to all researchers from both academic and industry at affordable rates.
010	
Title	McGill Chemistry Characterization (MC2) Facility
Authors	Fiurasek P., Levin K., Ramkaran M, Saadeh N., Sprules T., Titi H., Toader V., Wahba A
Location	Department of Chemistry, McGill University
Description	The McGill Chemistry Characterization (MC2) facility is a multi-user facility that provides instrumentation and expertise on a wide variety of analytical and microscopy techniques. We serve both experienced and novice investigators from academia and industry and our services include training for independent use, analytical services and full support from our experienced staff.
011	
Title	McGill Magnetic Resonance Facilities Helium Recovery System
Authors	Tara Sprules
Location	QANUC/Department of Chemistry, McGill University
Description	Helium is a non-renewable, critical mineral resource. In its liquid form, helium is essential for the operation of super-conducting magnets. It used in many other research and manufacturing fields. Due to its unique properties, it can be quite difficult to replace helium with other materials. In order to operate more sustainably, control costs, and protect expensive instrumentation from damage in the event of supply issues, the McGill Magnetic Resonance Facilities installed a Helium Recovery System to collect and recycle the liquid helium required to operate the eight magnets located in the scientific platform. On overview of the helium situation, and operation of the recovery system is presented.

012	
Title	illuminating the Brain: The Transformative Role of Flow Cytometry in Neuroscience
Authors	SIROIS Julien, LEPINE Paula, GOLDSMITH Taylor, SOUBANNIER Vincent, PISCOPO Valerio, DURCAN Thomas M.
Location	The Neuro's Early Drug Discovery Unit (EDDU), McGill University, Montreal, QC, Canada
Description	Flow cytometry, a powerful analytical technique originally developed for cell biology and immunology, has emerged as a valuable tool in the field of neuroscience. Flow cytometers can measure various characteristics of cells or particles, such as size, granularity, and the presence of specific proteins or nucleic acids. In the context of neuroscience, these capabilities can be harnessed to answer a wide range of questions. Here, at the Neuro's EDDU's Flow Cytometry Core, we mainly help investigators to (1) identify and quantify different neural cell types using specific markers, (2) isolate neuronal and glial cell subtypes for single-cell analysis and, (3) screen compounds for neuroprotection and regeneration. Also, we use powerful analysis pipelines better characterize these cell types. Ongoing research aims to integrate flow cytometry with other cutting-edge techniques, advancing our understanding of the brain.

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Figures:

Figure 1 – CNSP Scientific Platform Meeting (SPM) attendees in the lobby of the Neurological Institute ‘The Neuro’ in Montreal, Quebec, Canada. 114 attendees represent, 44 scientific platforms across Canada.

Figure 2 - Keynote Lecturer, Renee Whan give presentation entitled “Institutionally supported scientific platform and career path.”

Figure 3 - Plenary Talk, Mehrdad Hariri gives a presentation on the Canadian Science Policy Centre

Figure 4 – CNSP ‘Best Poster’ Winners, Left to Right: Jeffrey Seitz, Canada Biotech; Andrea I. Krahn from The Neuro's Early Drug Discovery Unit (EDDU); Claire Brown, president of the CNSP; and James Jonkman from University Health Network, Toronto, ON,